

Acta Futura 10 (2016) 121-129

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.202236

**Acta
Futura**

Concept Design of an Outpost for Mars Using Autonomous Additive Swarm Construction

SAMUEL WILKINSON,^{*} JOSEF MUSIL,[†] JAN DIERCKX,
IRENE GALLOU, AND XAVIER DE KESTELIER

SPECIALIST MODELLING GROUP, FOSTER+PARTNERS, RIVERSIDE, 22 HESTER RD, LONDON, UK

Abstract. Designing an outpost for a long-duration scientific expedition to an extreme environment such as Mars requires the basic qualities of functionality, comfort, and security. In this paper we assess: the key environmental conditions that govern the functionality of a Martian habitat; what it takes to design and build a comfortable home for a crew of four for 500 days with limited communication with Earth; and most critically, how to ensure mission success, safety, and robustness through increased redundancy. These factors are collected here into a conceptual design proposal, along with details of the deployment and multi-robot additive regolith construction system. This work is part of ongoing research at F+P specialist modelling group on robotics, large-scale additive construction, and architecture for extreme environments.

1 Introduction

As we move towards public or privately-funded human expeditions to Mars over the next few decades, it is necessary to consider what type of a home can be provided for astronauts on the surface of the planet; and that this endeavour should involve a broader multi-disciplinary

basis. In this paper our primary objective is to suggest that we have the technology to go beyond deploying a purely functional scientific base, as is perhaps the convention [7, 9]. Rather we propose to build a place for living, suitable for continued multi-mission occupation and development. It is more than likely that each successive expedition will incorporate feedback from the last into an evolving design. Any future colony is therefore likely to be a mixed system of technologies and habitats of increasingly advanced and successful design, the parents of which will be theoretical or prototyped closer to home.

Surface habitats can be one of three classes: Class I are single pre-fabricated pressurised module, such as the Apollo Lunar lander; Class II are multiple such modules connected together; and Class III combine multiple modules plus structures built from in-situ materials [10]. Extending this, Class IV would be constructed solely from local materials, and Class V the construction machines would themselves be fabricated in-situ.

Here, the proposed Class III outpost is a composite of light-weight inflatable pressurised modules [11] and a multi-robot additive construction system to compile local regolith into a protective heavy-weight shield. Although the pressurised elements are better suited to high accuracy fabrication possible under tightly controlled conditions on Earth, the compressive heavy-weight pro-

^{*}Corr. authors. E-mail: swilkinson@fosterandpartners.com,

[†]jmusil@fosterandpartners.com

FIGURE 1. Outpost design (axonometric view)

protective shield can be more heterogeneous. Therefore delivery of construction robots is lighter, more compact and flexible than sending an equivalent item from Earth. Others have also considered additive regolith construction processes for extra-planetary missions [6, 10, 12], along with other entries in NASA's 3D Printed Habitat Centennial Challenge.

The habitat (Figure 1) is divided into a network of connected deployable spaces with 120 m² habitable floor area divided into three modules. Each module has ~30 m² (plus two modules have upper mezzanine levels of ~15 m² each) and ~100 m³ habitable volume. The services for each includes 2.5 m³ of bulkhead required for the Environmental Control and Life Support Systems (ECLSS) which is located in the hard elements.

Conventionally, each module would be assigned a single specific task and the required equipment designed to fit [27]. Here, each of the modules is identical and is deployed empty; to be filled with specific equipment on

arrival of the crew. Each module can operate independently to provide basic life-support should another fail, and together provide a more comfortable environment.

1.1 Mission Architecture

The base and construction system is delivered prior to human arrival via two cargo ships containing: the deployable habitation units with their construction robots; a Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (RTG); and the In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU) module. These are to be delivered by launches of two heavy-lift rockets followed by a ~210 day transit [7]. On arrival in orbit, the subsequent stages of the delivery and deployment are as follows:

Entry, Descent, Landing

Descent of the modules will follow a similar method to the Pathfinder mission [3] with a combination

of ablative heat shield, solid retro-rockets, supersonic parachute, and finally air bags softening the final few metre drop. The modules have a dodecahedron shape ($\odot 4.6$ m), with each of the 12 faces covered in six inflated spheres ($\odot 1.35$ m). The EDL will happen in two phases: first the robots will be delivered to the surface for site selection and preparation; followed later by the habitat modules.

Surface Navigation

When developing the air bag system for the Pathfinder mission, rigorous drop-tests were conducted on various terrains, ranging from flat surfaces to steep, rocky inclines. This led to the use of multiple thin fabric layers rather than a single thick one. This greatly improved the strength since the outermost layer tore, absorbed energy, and created a soft protective buffer for the inner layers [5]. This study leads us to believe that the air bag system can be used for a secondary function post-EDL for positioning the modules.

Once stationary on the surface, the individual modules may be distributed within a landing radius of a few kilometres, and so it is necessary for them to navigate together. A sequenced inflation-deflation of the 72 external air bags starts a controlled roll of the modules to a shared target. The objective is to get within close proximity of one another (< 2 m) for the airlocks to connect. In order to ensure the modules face the correct way up, the individual rolling paths can be controlled over the journey to be slightly longer or shorter as required.

Robotic Site Preparation

The multi-robot system consists of three classes of robot deployed prior to the habitat modules (Figure 3): one large digger (RAC-D ~ 1 m); five medium transporters (RAC-T ~ 0.4 m); and fifteen small melters (RAC-M ~ 0.25 m). For system diversity, robot movement is by wheels, tracks and legs respectively.

The first task for the robot system once at the site is to excavate a 1.5 m deep hole for the habitat to sit within. The RAC-D robots will dig the loose regolith from the surface layer by layer, which will be moved nearby into protective berms by the RAC-T robots. The volume of excavated regolith is roughly equal to the amount to be printed on the shield.

Habitat Deployment and Connection

Once the site is prepared, and the three modules are gathered together, the small inflatable spheres surrounding the habitat partially deflate. The upper faces of the dodecahedron module fold up and lock in position, similarly for the lower faces to form the foundation which can fit to a rough landscape to ensure the interior floor is level. Subsequently, the core, shaped as a pentagonal prism, expands outwards (Figure 2).

Each of the five vertical faces of the core is either a connection or a window which will move to the outer perimeter along with the inflated skin. Once inflated the hard outer connections lock into the upper and lower pentagonal faces, and the connector airlocks extend outwards to connect to one another. Figure 2 shows this process of the modules in their prepared site, unfolding, inflating, and connecting. The three deployed habitat modules are now ready for the regolith shield to be constructed on top.

2 Extreme Environments

The first considerations in the design of a habitat are the challenges and affordances of the natural environment in which it is situated [4]. Although Mars has the closest similarities to Earth of any of the planets in the solar system, its environment is relatively inhospitable and presents challenges to human survival. In this section we assess how various environmental aspects will affect the design.

2.1 Site Selection

For solar power to be most effective and smaller temperature variations, an outpost should ideally be located nearer the equator. The multitude of scientifically interesting sites across Mars are situated in a broad range of topographical environments [7], from plains to caves, valleys, volcanoes, cliffs and craters. Special regions are less likely to occur in circum-equatorial regions [20] and the availability of ground-ice is likely to be greater in higher latitudes.

The system design and the outpost itself can be potentially applied to this broad range of cases. Whilst a specific site is not being selected, the broad 'river' estuary topography may offer certain benefits. The network of channels gives a directional catchment area for the EDL to focus on, although it may be more rugged terrain. After landing, the modules will navigate 'down-stream' to

FIGURE 2. Habitat module deployment: (right to left) unfolding, inflation, and connection.

a larger plain (for example, around 25°N 60°W).

2.2 Radiation

Due to the lower density atmosphere, lack of clouds, ozone and a magnetosphere, Mars receives more solar particle events (SPE) and galactic cosmic radiation (GCR) than Earth. Periodic radiation from SPE is especially harmful for humans, although these can be detected, given warning time, by solar observation. The constant bombardment of high-energy GCR particles delivers a lower yet steady dose rate compared with large SPEs that can deliver a very high dose over a short time. The GCR contribution to dose becomes more significant as the mission duration increases [17]. Mitigating radiation exposure for the crew is a serious consideration for the health and life-expectancy of the crew, and is the primary reason for the protective regolith shield.

2.3 Temperature

It is commonly reported that the temperature on Mars can reach a high of about 20°C at noon at the equator in the summer, or a low of about -153°C at the poles. In the mid-latitudes, the average temperature is about -50°C with a night-time minimum of -60°C and a summer midday maximum of about 0°C [22].

Due to the low density of the atmosphere, temperature is primarily governed by solar heating, and infrared cooling to the atmosphere and space, rather than conductive and convective heat transfer with the atmo-

sphere. This means radiative fluctuations, on a momentary, daily and yearly basis, are more varied and must be balanced with both adaptive thermal control systems and the heavy weight thermal mass of a regolith shield.

2.4 Ingress/Egress

It has been widely acknowledged that dust/dirt management is likely to be a key issue for long duration surface missions. The small particle size of the regolith could lead to contamination of the habitat and potential health risks to the crew. It is therefore important to control the ingress of dust. The suitport system [18] solves this issue, as well as removing the need for large airlocks, by having the spacesuit mounted externally. For EVAs the crew can climb into the back of the suits directly from the inside and detach themselves. The pressurised rover and conventional airlocks offer alternative points of entry if necessary.

Due to the low atmospheric pressure, high speed winds have minimal force yet are capable of transporting large amounts of electrically-charged dust over great distances. The deposition of dust around airlocks could potentially lead to difficult ingress/egress, therefore airlocks are distributed at various positions and angles to avoid entrapment. Suitports are used as the primary EVA method instead of traditional airlocks to remove risk of contamination of the interior with dust, and the exterior with bacteria.

2.5 Meteorites

The Martian atmosphere gives a certain degree of protection from micro-meteorite impact [28], however since the habitat is a pressurised volume, additional layers are needed to avoid breaches. The regolith shield gives an additional protective layer from micro-meteorites.

2.6 Life-support

Pressurised vessels are prone to breaches with the great pressure differential between inside and out. With atmospheric pressure 100-times less than Earth, a strong boundary is required which can withstand its occupants' activities. The tensile strength required to maintain this internal pressure is difficult to achieve with regolith which is more suitable for compressive structures [19]. Therefore a pre-fabricated multi-layered, woven Kevlar inflatable skin provides this pressure boundary.

Finally, for long duration missions it is important to maximise use of environmental resources for collection of energy, and production of life support consumables and rocket propellant. The In-situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU) unit which accompanies the habitat prior to human arrival has time to collect and process atmospheric carbon dioxide and potentially near-surface water ice [15]. Delivering the technology to produce propellant for crew return and life support consumables will be easier than delivering the gases/liquids themselves. Power for this processing will be delivered with the ISRU in the form of a Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generator (RTG) unit, to be supplemented by photovoltaic cells on crew arrival.

A human mission to Mars must necessarily be power-rich, in that life-support (ISRU) and everyday (primarily extra-vehicular) activities will require relatively high power when compared to previous low-activity missions. In this vein, power generation capability should be maximised at the mission outset to available weight limits, then expanded upon and diversified when possible on future missions.

3 Shelter

The second component of the concept design that we consider is security, in terms of both crew safety, peace of mind, and mission success in relation to the environmental conditions. Safety is arguably the most fundamental and primitive aspect of a home. Shelter from

wild animals, storms, enemies, and the cold has for thousands of years defined our homes. Protection from environmental conditions on Mars leads us to consider the necessity of a heavy-weight regolith shield.

A shield built from surface regolith has many advantages: protection from cosmic radiation, solar flares, dust storms, meteorites, and temperature variations; as well as increasing the durability of the light-weight habitat modules. Additionally, other protective structures can be built, such as berms, and other infrastructure like landing pads and roads.

3.1 Swarm Robotics

The construction system is comprised of three types of robot, each specialising in either excavation, transportation, or melting (Figure 3). The traditional approach to mission robotics is to consolidate risk and complexity into a single fate-sharing machine, with built-in redundancy (e.g. 'over-engineering' and system duplication). However, distributing risk across multiple specialised, simpler robots has the advantage of isolating risk to individual units. Given enough robots, there is also the potential for emergent behaviour, i.e. group behaviours greater than the sum of the individual behaviours [23, 24].

FIGURE 3. Construction robot classes: (large to small) RAC-D excavator, RAC-T transporter, and RAC-M melter.

Due to communications delays from Earth the robot control must be highly autonomous, with each individual being capable of decision-making and following rules. In the near future, it is predicted that computational intelligence and robotic technology will be sufficiently advanced to allow for a distributed system of autonomous intelligent machines. The system is capable of adapting to uncertain operating environments, of self-management and sys-

tem awareness, and of following high-level commands such as ‘explore’, ‘gather materials’ or ‘construct habitat’.

3.2 Additive Regolith Construction

The autonomous and generative additive construction method relies on rules and objectives, meaning that the outcome is more adaptive and open-ended. The regolith additive construction (RAC) approach is adapted for the low accuracy likely to be achieved from using variable materials at an uncertain site with autonomous robots in the field. The reliability of the RAC is in its simplicity, implemented by the three classes of robot: the strategy is to ‘dig, move, and melt’ regolith. The large digging robots will extract loose regolith in close proximity to the medium-sized mover robots to transport to the habitat. As the regolith is deposited, the smallest melting robots have a 200W microwave (2.45GHz) print head to bond one layer at a time [1]. The regolith is positioned into rough layers by the transporter robots, with the thickness continuously measured. Once a thin layer of regolith is in place, the third class of smallest robots selectively melts patches into a hard crystalline material (Figure 4).

For protection from radiation over long-term periods, rather than transporting heavy shielding from Earth, the construction of a regolith shield is a logical alternative [13]. The largest reduction in dose equivalent (rem) occurs in the first 20 g/cm^2 , so assuming a regolith density of 1.5 g/cm^3 the regolith depth should be at least 15 cm [21].

Whilst this is a minimum depth to ensure the crew does not receive ‘career limiting’ doses, the design includes 1.5 m above the work/sleep modules for general protection from cosmic radiation, and 2.5 m above the communal space for protection from solar flares during periods of increased solar activity.

The form of the regolith shield is driven by two key criteria, which become the operational rules for the individual robots. The first criteria is the minimal thickness of regolith needed to protect the inhabitants from radiation. The second criteria is the ability of all construction robots to transfer themselves to the highest layer printed so far during the construction process. As a result, multiple ramp structures blended into the overall form are introduced next to every opening of each module (airlocks, windows and suitports). Because of their location, they also serve as an extra protection of these openings.

FIGURE 4. Progression of regolith construction.

4 Comfort

The interior of the habitat will be the home for the four crew during their stay on Mars and should be, as a minimum, functional for the activities that can be expected and flexible enough to accommodate those that are unexpected. As the three initial habitat modules are deployed, connected and shielded, the concept was for the modules to be like an unfurnished apartment; all services are included but the furniture and more delicate internal equipment must be delivered with the crew. This has two benefits: first, that when the crew arrive they have an empty habitat that they can shelter in; and secondly that all of the interior can be configured or replaced as needed.

The use of three smaller modules instead of a single large one means that, in the circumstance that one is damaged, the other two would be adequate for continuing the (perhaps cramped) mission.

4.1 Private vs. Public

Sharing confined spaces for prolonged periods of times can potentially lead to conflict and psychological stress,

therefore it is important to manage the relationship between private and communal space [25]. The three modules, although identical on deployment, are differentiated during fit-out.

Module A, with full-height volume, is designated as the communal space, with exercise, cooking, communication and meeting space for four people (Figure 5). The

FIGURE 5. *Module A: communal space.*

other two modules B and C are designed for laboratory, work, toilet and cleaning facilities for two people on the lower levels (Figure 7), and individual private berthing quarters on the upper levels (Figure 6). This creates clear spaces for social interactions with the opportunity for privacy but not isolation [8].

FIGURE 6. *Module B/C upper: private quarters.*

4.2 Lighting

Humans have 24-hour day-night cycles hard-wired into them which should be maintained for long-term health and productivity [26]. Although there are a few small physical windows on airlocks for direct views out, the majority of lighting will be artificial. Circadian rhythm

FIGURE 7. *Module B/C lower: work space.*

lighting will adapt light levels and colour temperature throughout the day.

There will be a central 'skylight' in each module as primary lighting feature. The skylight will mimic the sun and the atmosphere using nanoparticles integrated into the transparent element [14] creating the perception of infinite depth improving the visual quality and comfort of the astronauts.

4.3 Surface Finishes

As with lighting, surface materials play a subtle but important role in occupants' enjoyment of an environment. Beyond strict functionality, materials can range from warm and natural through to cold and artificial. Throughout the habitat, natural materials have been placed in selected locations to create a greater feeling of home and, since monotony is a potential psychological issue, for visual and tactile stimulation [2]. For instance, wood veneer is placed on work surfaces, communal floors, and ladder steps; colourful woven fabrics and tatami mats are used in the sleeping quarters.

4.4 Acoustics

An additional source of psychological stress is the continual mechanical noise of life-support systems [25]. In this context, this can be particularly stressful as it is a constant reminder of the necessity of the life-support systems. Material selection is a simple way to reduce reverberation, with micro-perforated surfaces, soft finishes and vegetation on walls and ceilings.

5 Field Tests

There are a number of sites on Earth which have specific semblances to the Martian landscape, but the Atacama Desert to the west of the Andes has perhaps the most similar character [16]. The extremely arid and cold climate, isolation from human activity, similar soil, lack of microbial life, and desert landscape are the primary dominant features which would make for an interesting preliminary experimental site. Various analogous topographical features also exist for testing, such as plains, cliffs, caves and valleys.

FIGURE 8. *Outpost design*

It is envisaged that the developmental journey to Mars will probably, after Earth field tests, first involve testing technologies on the Moon. This test environment closer to home has many advantages, such as near-instant communication and far shorter journey time. However whilst the delivery components of the Mars mission architecture may not be applicable to a zero-g, no atmosphere scenario, the robotic additive construction can be rigorously tested.

The next developmental steps can be broken down into four parts: i) operation of the robotic system (detailed robot specification, autonomous control, communication, power beaming); ii) the additive construction process (material characterisation, filtering, melting process, layering); iii) the design of the habitat module itself; and iv) integration of the previous three components in the field.

Field tests on Earth may also pave the way for establishing whether this construction process is also applicable to terrestrial construction projects, such as in extreme environments or for infrastructural or disaster

relief.

6 Conclusion

Building on new frontiers demands reliable and tested solutions, whilst at the same time novel techniques are required to overcome unique challenges. In this context, the outpost design is an exploration of integrating existing viable space architectures and emerging robotic construction technologies. A semi-autonomous multi-robot construction system is used to collect and assemble a highly robust Mars habitat prior to arrival of the first crew. The use of regolith additive construction and inflatable architecture provide an adaptive and open-ended strategy to master broad uncertainties in the terrain and resources of Mars.

Acknowledgements

This work was entered in the AmericaMakes 3D Printed Habitat design competition, one of NASA's Centennial Challenges. We would like to thank the following companies and individuals for their assistance during the competition: Penelope Boston at New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology, Astrobotic Technology, Malika Beggour, John Eager of the British Antarctic Survey, David A. Green of King's College London, and Rapha Clothing.

References

- [1] M. Barmatz, D. Steinfeld, M. Anderson, et al. 3d microwave print head approach for processing lunar and mars regolith. In *Lunar and Planetary Science Conference*, volume 45, page 1137, 2014.
- [2] I. Biederman and E. Vessel. Perceptual pleasure and the brain: A novel theory explains why the brain craves information and seeks it through the senses. *American Scientist*, 94(3):247–253, 2006.
- [3] R. D. Braun and R. M. Manning. Mars exploration entry, descent and landing challenges. In *Aerospace Conference, 2006 IEEE*, pages 18–pp. IEEE, 2006.
- [4] H. G. K. Broughton and I. I. H. Vi. Antarctic Research Stations: Parallels for Interplanetary Design. pages 1–12, 2010.

- [5] D. Cadogan, C. Sandy, and M. Grahne. Development and evaluation of the mars pathfinder inflatable airbag landing system. *Acta Astronautica*, 50(10):633–640, 2002.
- [6] G. Cesaretti, E. Dini, X. De Kestelier, et al. Building components for an outpost on the lunar soil by means of a novel 3d printing technology. *Acta Astronautica*, 93:430–450, 2014.
- [7] B. G. Drake, S. J. Hoffman, and D. W. Beaty. Human exploration of mars, design reference architecture 5.0. In *Aerospace Conference, 2010 IEEE*, pages 1–24. IEEE, 2010.
- [8] S. Häuplik-Meusburger. *Architecture for astronauts: an activity-based approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2011.
- [9] S. J. Hoffman. The Mars Surface Reference Mission: A Description of Human and Robotic Surface Activities. Technical report, 2001.
- [10] A. S. Howe, C. McQuin, J. Townsend, et al. Faxing Structures to the Moon: Freeform Additive Construction System (FACS). *AIAA*, 5437:10–12, 2013.
- [11] K. J. Kennedy, J. Raboin, G. Spexarth, et al. Inflatable Structures Technology Handbook. In *Habitation*, volume 1. 2000.
- [12] B. Khoshnevis, M. P. Bodiford, K. H. Burks, et al. Lunar contour crafting—a novel technique for isru-based habitat development. In *43rd AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit—Meeting Papers*, pages 7397–7409, 2005.
- [13] J. Kozicki. Human friendly architectural design for a small martian base. *Advances in Space Research*, 48(12):1997–2004, 2011.
- [14] P. Marks. Blue skies on tap, whenever you need them. *New Scientist*, 222(2965):21, 2014.
- [15] A. C. Muscatello and E. Santiago-Maldonado. Mars In Situ Resource Utilization Technology Evaluation. *50th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting Including the New Horizons Forum and Aerospace Exposition*, 2012.
- [16] R. Navarro-González, F. A. Rainey, P. Molina, et al. Mars-like soils in the atacama desert, chile, and the dry limit of microbial life. *Science*, 302(5647):1018–1021, 2003.
- [17] D. Rapp. Radiation effects and shielding requirements in human missions to the moon and mars. *International Journal of Mars Science and Exploration*, 2:46–71, 2006.
- [18] B. Romig and C. Allton. First generation suit port development and testing. *Johnson Space Center Engineering Directorate Biennial Report*, 2009.
- [19] F. Ruess, J. Schaenzlin, and H. Benaroya. Structural design of a lunar habitat. *Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, 19(July 2015):133–157, 2006.
- [20] J. D. Rummel, D. W. Beaty, M. A. Jones, et al. A new analysis of Mars “special regions”: findings of the second MEPAG Special Regions Science Analysis Group (SR-SAG2). *Astrobiology*, 14(11):887–968, 2014.
- [21] L. C. Simonsen and J. E. Nealy. Radiation protection for human missions to the moon and mars. Technical report, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Hampton, VA (USA). Langley Research Center, 1991.
- [22] J. E. Tillman. Mars temperature overview. <https://goo.gl/k0ofvT>, 2009.
- [23] W. Truszkowski, M. Hinchey, and J. Rash. NASA’s Swarm Missions: The challenge of building autonomous software. *IT Professional*, (6.5):47–52, 2004.
- [24] W. Truszkowski, M. Hinchey, J. Rash, et al. Autonomous and autonomic systems: A paradigm for future space exploration missions. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, 36(3):279–291, 2006.
- [25] D. A. Vakoch. Psychology of space exploration. *Washington (DC): NASA*, 2011.
- [26] A. R. Webb. Considerations for lighting in the built environment: Non-visual effects of light. *Energy and Buildings*, 38(7):721–727, 2006.
- [27] A. Whitmire, L. Leveton, H. Broughton, et al. Minimum acceptable net habitable volume for long-duration exploration missions. 2015.
- [28] S. Wright. Infrared analyses of small impact craters on earth and mars. *University of Pittsburgh*. Archived from the original on June, 12, 2007.
